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Photographic Evolution: An Analysis of Old School Processing in Contrast to Modern Graphic Editing

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Photographic Evolution: An Analysis of Old School Processing in Contrast to Modern Graphic Editing

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ABSTRACT

The art of photography has taken a long time to be developed as it what it is now, showing truly a product of tireless experimentation of testing to see how the world looks and how it can be recorded through glimpses of the moments that are happening to people. Here in this paper, the researcher wants to analyze the techniques of developing old school photos in comparison to rasterized graphic editing in the form of Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, a versatile software for developing photos for many purposes. After the analysis of the two subjects, it is noteworthy that the techniques of the past using film cameras and darkroom developing, specifically through the development of the chemical and physical properties, still has reflected some important aspects through the development of modern graphic editing in rasterized photos, such in the form of the different panels and setting that are found in the develop module in Adobe Photoshop Lightroom.

Keywords: *photography, photograph development, Adobe Photoshop Lightroom*

INTRODUCTION

The advancements in technology have come a long way since the documentation of the first-ever photo that was taken by French Joseph Nicéphore Niépce that dates back in 1826 or 1827, entitled “*View from the Window at Le Gras*”. In the modern day, however, it is totally easy to have your photo be printed with just a simple tap at a smartphone with a camera on it, then send the raw files to a computer with a printer booted in as a tertiary device. Alongside with the advancements of technology, comes the dwindling of old techniques that were used in order to make photographs or films. While these methodologies are still practiced by those people who are really passionate in the art of photography, it is now becoming obsolete because of the major headways in technology in enhancing the inclinations of the camera. While it is a trend to have a polaroid camera or a single lens reflex (SLR) camera to be used for personal purposes, developing those pictures is not the same as those developed in a digitized version.

Without the knowledge of understanding the physical and chemical processes in developing photographs, the development of a single photo may look fascinating to the common person. With the advancements of chemistry, grasping the gist behind the chemistry of photography is known to be established on photosensitivity and reactions with light. The processes behind these create a traditional photograph, which starts from the camera from the absorption of photons. After this, the process is continued in a darkroom, which heavily involves organic chemistry and acid-base chemistry principles. The structures of the reagents in the development phase are also crucial as it may affect the quality of final photograph. The film that is also utilized for the production of the photo is also composed of materials that are specific to the creation of the pictures.

Now with the betterment of this process, the time needed to process out these photos are reduced to a much more minimal time, allowing the publishing of many photos that can be used to document and tell stories, finally allowing the art of photography to emerge. In addition, the old techniques of photo processing is now replaced with application software that can be downloaded in a computer, where all of the processing to have a photo be developed is now on the hands of everyone with said computer applications. In this paper, the researcher will take upon the look of Adobe Photoshop

Lightroom, commonly known as Lightroom or Adobe Lightroom. This is an application on the current Adobe Creative Cloud (CC) bundle and is updated annually with a few changes, mostly focusing on improving the quality and of the photos in the development module. Specifically, this paper will analyze on two different methodologies of processing photographs in two different time periods by studying the physical, chemical, and digital properties. The paper only limits itself to conventional photo processing developments using film and darkroom in comparison to a recent version of Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, which is Creative Cloud 2020 Version 9.4.

Research Question

How does the physical and chemical processes of producing and developing old photographs can be likened and compared to modern-day photo developing processes?

Research Design

The current study that is being done by the researcher is following the mixed methods research, which inherits qualities from qualitative and quantitative studies. The researcher decides to continue with this method because of the limitations that are pressed on by the ongoing pandemic, which made the researcher's home region to be on a strict lockdown measure with an imposing curfew every night.

Research Objectives

- Explore the chemistry and physics behind the nature of photography by analyzing the processes in the technical aspects of old school photograph development.
- Discover possible connections to the processing and developing techniques that are found in modern graphic editing application softwares in relation to old school photograph development.
- Explain, if possible, the significant relation of the connections of the two methodologies in photograph development.

Hypothesis:

In this study, the researcher constructed a null and an alternative hypothesis from what will the paper be going to when moving forward to the actual basis of the study.

H₀: The analysis of the methodologies in old school photo processing and developing does have a significant connection to the processing and developing techniques in modern graphic editing application softwares.

H_a: The analysis of the methodologies in old school photo processing and developing do not possess a significant connection to the processing and developing techniques in modern graphic editing application softwares.

Thesis Statement

With the improvement of technologies involving capturing photographs, investigating old technologies that are based in films and darkrooms in order to develop in contrast to the newer technologies, taken will full engagement to the disparities, modern day methodologies in graphic editing nowadays possesses an extensive connection and is associated to each other.

Conceptual Framework

For this paper's conceptual framework, the graph that is shown below is a depiction of what the researcher is going to do when tackling about the connection between conventional photographic development and modern photographic applications in the development of photographs in two different time periods.

Figure 1.1: The conceptual framework made by the researcher for the current study. Involving the analysis of two different methodologies in the development in photographs. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

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REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Background History of Cameras

In the very essence of the art and manner of photography is a camera. Cameras are sealed boxes that are equipped with an aperture, a tiny gaping hole that allows light in to capture an image on a light-sensitive surface, such as a film, or a digital sensor. In order to control the amount of light that reaches into the camera, they have various mechanisms to control how the light falls onto the light-sensitive surface. The ones that focus the entering light of the camera are the lenses, while other mechanisms by which the size of the aperture can be widened or narrowed to let more or less light into the camera, and a shutter mechanism determines the amount of time the photo-sensitive surface is exposed to the light (Wikipedia, 2021).

The word "*camera*" comes from "*camera obscura*", a device that was made during the Renaissance that was a vanguard to the modern-day photographic cameras that people have in their possession. The "*camera obscura*" (which literally means "dark room") consisted of a darkened chamber with a diminutive hole in one wall. Images from outside the camera passed through this hole, which acted the lens, appeared inverted through the opposite wall. Reduced in size, this became the pinhole camera; lenses and photographic plates were added in the 19th century to create the photographic camera (Encyclopedia.com, 2018).

The basics of the cameras that we are still using today is through the lens. The lenses focus everything to the camera in order to give an image. A lens is a tool used to

bring light to a fixed focal point. The lens is what focuses light through the viewfinder into a film, DSLR, or mirrorless camera. If the lens was removed from the camera, the image that will only be reproduced is white light (MasterClass.com, 2021).

Figure 2.1: A remake of the wooden *camera obscura*, an old model that will soon be recognized as the forerunner of cameras. (Source: widewalls.ch)

Types of Cameras

Before, the most common camera that existed is the film camera, with a 35 mm film that was behind it. Medium format film cameras provide an even bigger surface frame (up to 4 times bigger than the usual 35mm, but smaller than large format) and is widely-used by gallery artists for its capability to develop huge prints without losing image quality and to capture natural-looking, wide-angle shots as our eyes actually see them in the real world. However, with the up-and-coming expansion of digital sensors during the 21st Century, many cameras have been developed such as 360-degree cameras, action

cameras, mirrorless cameras, and digital single lens reflex (DSLR) cameras (adorama.com, 2017).

Figure 2.2: Types of cameras that are utilized in the field of photography and in film making. (Source: StudioBinder.com)

Traditional Photographic Development

A photographic film is an object that records a still image when exposed to light. Typically, this is arranged in a camera, and light from the image being shot is left to enter to concentrate through. The lenses in the camera may also affect the substantiation of the amount of light entering in. The film is exposed to the image by opening a shutter in the camera body, and the succession of the shutter and film speed establishes the amount of light that strikes the film (MadeHow.com, 2021).

After a film has been prepared, the process is then turned into the stages of development and fixing. The photographic developer, also called as a developer, is a chemical or a mixture of chemicals that react upon an image in order to convert the invisible images that are shown on film into a visible image. This usually comprises of chemicals that are placed in an aqueous solution (solutions that are mixed with water). A

special trait of these developers is that they act more quickly if the photo being developed is being exposed to light (Karlheinz et. al., 2000). As the development of the film has made the image clear, the only thing remaining to do is by fixing the photo. This is done to avoid the particles that were used during the whole process to affect the photo over some time, which may cause in blurring out the said image. By fixation, the film or paper is impervious to any further action sustained by exposing it to light (Karlheinz et. al., 2000).

Modern Photographic Development

Films however, are going to be replaced with the introduction of a better and stronger competitor, the digital camera sensor (DCS). Being advantageously small in size and can fit into smaller variations of cameras out there, the digital camera is a versatile sensor that has two main functionalities in order for it to work, the first by creation of a grayscale photograph, and the second way will produce a full-color image.

A DCS creates a grayscale photo when you decide to take the picture and press the button. Then they are exposed to light, which opens up the light cavities in a digital camera in order to collect photons stored as an electrical signal. After the exposure has been completed, the camera will shut the cavities down. Once these are closed, the camera will instantaneously total up how many photons entered each cavity which is done by measuring how strong the signals are. These are then distributed with precise digital values and create a grayscale image because each cavity cannot distinguish how many of each color they have.

The way these values become so precise is because the camera does the aspect termed "bit depth" to determine them. As a common rule with modern cameras, each cavity can only capture one out of three primary colors (red, blue, and green). This aspect lets the camera know how many are available to it in its palette that is determined by the numbers of 0's and 1's used to identify each one. In terms of grayscale images, the bit depth will identify the possible unique tones, instead of colors. When the file format has been recorded, the exactness that was performed can be further diminished (LifePixel.com, 2020).

Figure 2.3: A standard film roll used in motion pictures. (Source: offidocs.com)

Application for Image Development: Adobe Photoshop Lightroom

The software that the researcher would compare to traditional photo developing methods is the well-known Adobe Photoshop Lightroom. This software is a rasterized image editor, designed for productive image classification and administration system that is developed and still currently being improved by Adobe Inc. The editing functions that can be found on the said software includes color balance, toning, presence, color grading, detail, lens corrections, photo corrections, filters, and adjustment brushing (Mosaic.com, 2012). Development of the current Lightroom started in 1999 (Schewe, 2006), but only in 2006, the team that was behind the project had decided to start the beta of the project in Macintosh systems. The project also found a boost after acquiring the technology behind Rawshooter, an image processing software that was designed by the company Pixmantec (Digital Photography Review, 2006).

In 2007, Adobe announced that the first version of Lightroom will be released as a software as a service (SaaS) with a perpetual charge (greaterthangatsby.com, 2016). Fast forward to modern times, the continuous development and reputation of the software

have changed the software during the rise of the Adobe Creative Cloud (CC) Services. After then, the first variant of the Adobe Photoshop Lightroom CC that was published in 2017 then became the first iteration of the software that is not available with a permanent license (imaging-resource.com, 2017).

Synthesis

The above review of related literature suggests that there are a lot of changes coming from the times of old photographic development up to the computer-based techniques for photographic development that are present today. The review also suggests that there is still a bleak gap between the developments of editing technologies coming from the time of photographic development transitioning from film to computer-based formats.

METHODOLOGY

Old School Photographic Development

Material Analysis of Photographic Development

This section of the paper will detail about the materials used for the development of a photo. From this section, the physical and the chemical properties of the necessary chemicals and objects that were used were analyzed carefully for the next section of the current study that was undertaken.

Material Analysis of Photographic Paper and Film

The photographic paper and film that was used before in photography consist of a gelatinized emulsion of silver halide grains, a compound made of silver and a halogen. A silver halide, also known as a silver salt, is a chemical compound that is produced by silver and a halogen, notably silver bromide (AgBr), silver chloride (AgCl), silver iodide (AgI), silver subfluoride or disilver monofluoride (Ag₂F), silver (I) fluoride or

argentous fluoride (AgF), silver (II) fluoride or argentic fluoride (AgF_2), and silver (III) fluoride or silver trifluoride (AgF_3).

Figure 3.1: Three - dimensional (3D) lattice figures of silver halide (AgX) structures. (Source: Benjah-bmm27)

This liniment is then layered onto the base of a photographic film or paper. The halides that are used for the grains are chlorine (Cl), bromine (Br), and iodine (I), although bromine is the most prevalent among the three. The grains are crystalline structures of silver ions and halide ions that form a lattice, which can be described as a regular arrangement of their particles because the overall attractive interactions between particles are maximized, and the total intermolecular energy is minimized, when the particles pack in the most efficient manner. This arrangement of these structures in the atomic scales can be viewed at a microscopic level (OpenStax, 2020). Despite being stabilized, there is still some movement allowed of atoms and electrons throughout the structure.

There are two main energy levels that are present in the grain, which are the valence band and the conduction band. Those electrons that are present in the valence band are localized, while the electrons in the conduction band are free to move through the grain. When photons from light come into contact with a silver halide grain, an electron is discharged from the valence band of the halide into the conducting band of the structure. This electron will then combine with a moving silver ion, thus forming atomic silver (Ag). The place where this occurs is the latent image center, where the negative photographs are formed during the process. When three or four of these events occur at the same location, an aggregate of silver metal is produced. The said number of atoms are necessary for the stabilization of the latent image center. The grains themselves are a cluster of silver of halide ions, making this process to be repetitive when they come in contact with light.

Figure 3.2: Formation of a single silver atom (Ag) from a silver halide (AgX) at the latent image center when exposed to light. (Source: Nichole Witten)

The formed latent image is invisible to the eye at first, but eventually further development will create dark areas from the atomic silver due to its color. This serves as a catalyst for the development in the darkroom, a blank room where pictures are hanged

for the photos to formally develop. Silver formation during this process is logarithmically proportional to the intensity of light that enters it. Therefore, the areas where the emulsion is exposed to more light will have more latent image centers and appear darker on the film. In formulating the print, light is shown through the negative, so areas that were originally dark then receive less light and appear brighter.

Material Analysis of Photographic Developers

Commercial photographic developers are composed of four different components: the developing agent, the accelerator, the restrainer, and the preservative. The developing agent is a reducing agent to the silver halides in order to change it into metallic silver. The reducing agents present in the developer also give up electrons in the process. This is how photograph development is chemically accelerated at places in the photo that are vivid and shunned in places that received little to no stimulation. This process however, is expected to be much faster to occur in those that already have silver in the latent image center.

The reaction that occurs in the developing agent is a reduction - oxidation reaction. With the developer donating electrons to advance the process, it oxidizes. The effectivity of this process can also be halted with the presence of oxygen. This comes the role of the preservative, as it slows the process of that happens to the latent image center as well as preventing it from oxidized.

Figure 3.3: Commercial photographic developer formulas for developing high - quality photographs. (Source: photo60studio.com)

Accelerators are agents that are present in the developer that makes the developing solution more basic or alkaline, as accelerators are basic solutions. The solution of the accelerators deprotonates the reducing agent, freeing up electrons to be donated, thus speeding up the process of development. On the other hand, restrainers are agents that stop the processing of the developing agent in order for it not to develop too quickly.

The commercial developers are mostly developed by Kodak, with developer variants such as the Eastman Kodak D-76 film developer, D-72 print developer, and D-96 motion picture negative developer as the forerunning solutions that were used for development. Popular developing agents that were used in solutions are metol (monomethyl-p-aminophenol hemisulfate), phenidone (1-phenyl-3-pyrazolidinone), dimezone (4,4-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazolidin-3-one), and hydroquinone (benzene-1,4-diol). Other developing agents in use are glycin (N-(4-hydroxyphenyl) glycine), pyrogallol (benzene-1,2,3-triol), and catechol (1,2-dihydroxybenzene). When used in low sulfite developer composition, the latter two compounds cause gelatin to harden and stain in the vicinity of developing grains. Generally, the optical density of the stain increases in the heavily exposed (and heavily developed) area. In the early days of photography, a wide range of developing agents were used, including chlorhydroquinone ($C_6H_5ClO_2$), iron (II) oxalate or ferrous oxalate (FeC_2O_4), hydroxylamine (NH_2OH), iron (II) lactate or ferrous lactate ($C_6H_{10}FeO_6$), and iron (II) citrate or ferrous citrate ($FeC_6H_6O_7$).

The commercial accelerators that are commonly used in solutions are sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), sodium tetraborate or borax, or sodium hydroxide to create the appropriately high potential of hydrogen (pH). Restrainers that are commonly used in solutions are sodium sulfite, although homemade films that contain common acids such as caffeic acid and ascorbic acid can also be used for homemade films.

In the development of colored films, the processes that are used for the development uses other agents, which are explored by photo developing companies like Kodak and Fuji. Examples of the processes that are developed are the C-41 and C-22

processes. Reversal developments in film include solutions containing phenidone ($C_9H_{10}N_2O$) and hydroquinone-monosulfonate ($C_6H_6O_2 \cdot SO^{-3}$). The process is quite similar to black and white photograph development, with differences in applying the developer solutions and other additional steps that are required to develop the photo.

Figure 3.4: Some of the common developing agents that are used in commercial developer formulas for photographs. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Material Analysis of Photographic Fixers

Photographic fixers are then applied to the developed picture in order to dissolve the molecules of silver halide that were unexposed on the paper or film after the period of development. This is a way of conserving the state of the image because the silver halide grains can be further reduced by sunlight and thus botching the status of the image formed. This degradation causes a purple hue on the along with the loss of finer details. Silver halides are insoluble in water, so a reaction coming from typical fixers like sodium thiosulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) and ammonium thiosulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$). The fixers create a complex ion where the remaining grains would then dissolve. Although they are practically insoluble, a minimal portion of dissociated silver and halide ions will be present after the occurrence of the reaction. The complex ion that is formed with the fixer is thus more stable than the silver ion, which means that more of it is created and less atomic silver will be left as the halides strive to maintain equilibrium.

Along with fixers, there are also additives that are added into the mix such in the form of hardeners, which prevent the swelling of grains on the paper that would make the surface softer but easily susceptible to damage. Additive hardeners sustain better in acidic environments, and will further stop the development if a developer solution is placed onto a stop bath. Acids, which support hardeners, are also added to some fixers. There are also non-thiosulphate fixers made for special purposes. Processing of fixers are all available in all types of photograph development, including black-and-white films, Kodachrome (Kodak), and chromogenic (colorized) films.

Figure 3.5: Commercially used photographic fixers. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Material Analysis of Stop Baths and Wash

While the developer will take out the image captured on the film, it will carry on improving the picture until it is stopped. This will ruin the film and is what is referred to as overexposure. If the film has been developed to a proper degree, the developer is changed with a stop bath. The stop bath balances the developer and stops the film from becoming overexposed. One of the most commonly used chemicals in stop baths is acetic acid. Besides, the developer could also be washed off with water; using acetic acid is both quicker and more thorough.

Figure 3.6: Photographic print washing in a homemade set. The particles are settled towards the bottom during the rinsing of the photographs in the washing set-up.
(Source: shootitwithfilm.com)

Washing the photographs with water is important during the end of the developing and fixing processes as it only leaves out the photo that is being produced, whether the final product is grayscale or chromogenic, as it eradicates undesirable and exhausted

processing substances which, if left in situ, may cause deterioration and demolition of the produced image. The chemical solutions that are also used during the process of developing as well as fixing photos also have irritative effects to the body, so disposing any trace amounts of the used chemicals must be a priority to the processing of photographs.

Using thiosulfate-based fixers has the disadvantage of it dissolving the silver particles at a very slow rate. Insufficient washing of the photo can lead to the lingering trace amounts of the used fixer can slowly bleach or stain the developed images. Photograph prints that are printed upon high quality fiber papers must be rinsed in clean, cold water for up to 40 minutes depending on the utilized material. For modern resin coated papers, washing for as little as two minutes in warm water can be already satisfactory to abolish residual fixer left on the image. Hypo cleaning agents or also known as washing aids, can also be applied to the photograph in order to erase all the fixer that has been accumulated during the fixing process.

Traditional darkroom practices states that films must be washed for about 30 minutes or longer, with water being changed for about three times during the process. This is not applicable when the used fixer is a non - hardening one. Despite the fact that washing is important to the stability of the film over the course of time, excessive washing to the photos is destructive to the images as minimal amounts of thiosulfate in very small concentrations has shown a beneficial effect on the longevity of the photographs.

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom – Develop Module

Adobe Lightroom

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, better known as Lightroom, is a raw converter that manages the file type in the background. Other application softwares like the well-known Adobe Photoshop, have chances to convert the file types first before doing any other editing in the necessary software. Lightroom supports images in all kinds of formats. Some of them include Tagged Image File Format (TIFF), Digital Negative (DNG), and

Joint Photographers Experts Group (JPEG) formats. But it's also compatible with Canon Control Register 2 (CR2) and Nikon Electronic Format (NEF) files.

Figure 3.7: The Adobe Photoshop Lightroom CC Installer and the shortcut icon in the desktop after it was installed. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The software is also where most aspiring photographers start their journey in photo editing. Anything that is related to making photos simply look better and enjoyable to watch is possible in this software as it is straightforward to use along with a neat user interface that allows the user to organize and process their pictures, as well as directly printing and sharing the said files.

Later version of the software also included creating a virtual photobook for the photos, which is included in the version that the researcher is now using (Adobe Photoshop Lightroom CC Version 9.4). The software is best recognized for in its non-destructive editing feature. That means you can reset the settings and adjustments so you can work on the original photo again. Lightroom focuses on speed when working with

a lot of images. The program acts as a library, with easily accessible folders that you can organize. Simple clicks allow you to process an image then use those same settings over many images.

Figure 3.8 - 3.9: The landing page features of Adobe Photoshop Lightroom in the Library Module. In Figure 3.9, the photos are shown to be organized in the Library Module in an organized file format. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Color Corrections

The first panel that a user of the Adobe Photoshop Lightroom software is the primary color corrections, which is also called the Basic panel. From here, the user can choose to increase or decrease the temperature and the level of tint, exposure level and contrast level, highlights and shadows, as well as whites and blacks. The user interface for the panel is also just the same with the other panels to be discussed, as it only utilizes a slider for most of the parts, ranging from -100 to 100. The user can also manually select the number required for the lightroom adjustment (Rodriguez-Martinez, 2020).

Figure 3.10: A photo being manipulated only by using the basic color corrections panel in Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #1): *Temp: +40, Tint: +50, Exposure: -1.25, Contrast: +20, Highlights: +45, Shadows: -55, Whites: -35, Blacks: -55*

Tone Curve

Just below the basic color corrections for the Develop Module is the tone curves panel, a nifty tool that can affect the inclusive brightness and contrast of a picture. Adjustments made on the panel also works like the color corrections panel, such as making images brighter or darker, and affect the contrast levels. Besides, it also represents all the tones of your image. The bottom axis of the panel is the Tone axis: the line starts from the shadows at the left and highlights at the right-most part. The only problem considered for the panel as of this version is the lack of support in vector graphics, as Adobe Photoshop Lightroom only supports non-destructive raster photo editing (Gay, 2018).

Figure 3.11: Photos being developed only in the tone curves panel in Adobe Lightroom's Develop Module. The first one is manipulated uniformly and the second one is manipulated via adjusting the red, blue, and green tone curves.

Develop Changes (Photo #2): Highlights: +5, Lights: -80, Darks: -45, Shadows: -50

Develop Changes (Photo #3): Red: 61/66, 68/74, 78/89, 187/193;

Blue: 100/79, 167/133, 179/181; Green: 56/51, 177/167

Hue, Saturation, and Luminance (HSL) Color Sliders

This panel is used for the adjustment of color in Adobe Lightroom. Here, the user can play out with the amount of hue (color), which changes the colors of the original photo to the other colors that are found on the edges of the color wheel, saturation, the power of the hue, and luminance, which states how bright the hues are (Holtzer, 2020).

Figure 3.12: A photo being adjusted only by using the HSL/Color panel in Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #4): Orange: -85, Yellow: -35, Blue: -85, Purple: -65

Split Toning

This panel in the Adobe Lightroom's Develop Module allows photographers to add a color tint to the shadows and highlights on separate occasions in the same photograph. The split toning option in Lightroom affixes a golden glow to the light in a photo, cool down shadows, mimic film, influence mood, or add a sepia effect. However, the split-toning acclimation can stick out in the image, particularly when the saturation sliders are pushed to the bounds, many veteran users of Lightroom would tell not to adjust the saturation sliders too much or else the photo would adapt to the tints added (Cox, 2018).

Figure 3.13: A photo being attuned using the split toning panel in Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #5): Highlights: Hue 245, Saturation 79, Balance +85; Shadows: Hue 37, Shadow 60

Detail Corrections

The fifth panel is mainly used to set to fix images with backlighting problems. This means that it is the panel that is best used for fine-tuning photos with silhouetted images due to strong backlighting or modifying subjects that have been minimally washed out as they are way too close to the camera flash. Adjustments in this panel is also good for brightening areas of shadow in a well-lit image (Row, 2016).

Figure 3.14: A photo being slightly changed using detail corrections panel in Adobe Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #6): Exposure: -0.25, Contrast: +25, Highlights: -55, Shadows: -30, Sharpening: Amount 75, Radius 2.0, Detail 45, Masking 85, Color 25

Lens Corrections

This is a panel that is within Lightroom's Develop Module that allows finalizes such lens problems as deformity, chromatic aberration, vignetting and perspective correction “non-destructively”, without quitting Lightroom. One of the drawbacks of this tool is that it is lens-specific. As each model is designed with a specific optical formula, lens application must also be uniquely customized for better corrections (Mansurov, 2019).

Figure 3.15: A photo being slightly changed using detail corrections panel in Adobe Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #7): HUAWEI Lens: P40 Pro Rear Telephoto; Profile: Adobe, Exposure: -0.95, Contrast: +25, Highlights: +20, Whites: -25; Highlights: Hue 65, Saturation 55

HDR Effects

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom has also built-in effects for maximizing the feel of photos that were taken. For example, the photo can be added with a touch of vignette in order to “highlight” the subject, adding it with grain in order to make the photo look like it has been tarnished by excessive grains. This along with other panels explained can make the photo look professionally stunning and print-ready. (PhotographyPla.net, 2015).

Figure 3.16: A photo developed by only using the effects panel in Adobe Lightroom’s Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

**Develop Changes (Photo #8): Exposure: -1.20, Contrast: +25, Highlights: -50, Shadows: -40;
Style: Amount -45, Midpoint 65, Roundness +56, Feather 30, Highlights 45;
Grain: Amount 25, Size 45, Roughness 70**

Camera Calibration

The function of this panel is to assist the user to amend to the colors of the photos, as well as mend undesirable color casts from a bad lighting environment. Different light sources make different color curves, which can be amended by using the hue, saturation and shadow sliders inside of the camera calibration panel. It remedies the blandness of color in photos, and make unique light responses that is similar to neutralizing the balance of color (Breitkrutz, 2020).

Figure 3.17: A photo developed by only using the effects panel in Adobe Lightroom's Develop Module (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo).

Develop Changes (Photo #9): Exposure: -1.10, Tint: -45; Red Primary: Hue +50, Saturation +60; Blue Primary: Hue +15, Saturation +60; Green Primary: Hue +50, Saturation 0

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Presets

Presets are a configuration of settings that are planned to attain a certain look on images that are developed under Adobe Photoshop Lightroom. Presets lessen the time it takes to find the perfect combinations to add on to the right photos. As such, the aesthetic of using presets into the work is the consistency of style, time-management, and simplicity they bring to your editing sessions. Despite all of this, most of the presets require a form of payment as selling presets are considered as a high-value digital market (Groves, 2020). Because of the demand and the high market for it, the researcher cannot find a preset for Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, as it requires payment. Another problem for this is the time constraints for this paper, so if there is any free preset that can be found, it will still take some time to get into it and make sure the application is working.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interestingly, this analysis details the increase of the capabilities in producing and developing photographs throughout the period of time. The story of the camera has been related to the need of creating memories and reminiscing memories. It has been noted by the researcher that throughout the observations during the utilization of the Adobe Photoshop Lightroom develop module, some panels have similarities on the development and fixing stages of conventional photographic film processing.

As an example, the photographic film, constructed of transparent plastic in a shape of a strip or sheet and it has one side covered with light-sensitive silver halide crystals made into a gelatinous emulsion (Better, 2020) that is used in photographic cameras for recording images. When exposed to light by a photographic camera, it transforms depending on the amount of light engrossed by each crystal. These changes make an undetectable latent image in the emulsion, which is then anchored and developed into a visible photograph (photographyhistoryfacts.com, 2021).

Despite films are getting popular yet again due to the aesthetic of gaining photographs directly to pose as a memory, the digitization of processes still had hit hard on films. However, film effects in applications like Adobe Photoshop Lightroom have taken a nod to it, such with the effects where the photos can be adjusted (Groves, 2020) with quite the right number of adjustments in the sliders order to mimic a film. Other photo adjustment tools may have also done the same using filters to mimic the ways of the past involving darkroom and film-based approaches.

Improvement of the art and science behind the works of photographic art has truly come a long way. Before modern applications, developers carry out most of the work by ionizing the silver halides in the film. It has made companies and experimenters in the field of photography to create the right mix in order to balance out the pH levels of the in order for the developing agents to achieve this conversion by reducing the silver halides as efficiently as possible. This can be also reflected upon the development of the presets in Lightroom, as they have the same methods, and also due to the fact that Adobe Photoshop Lightroom is also the industry standard of photographic development.

Fixing using photographic fixers is the final process in developing the film for photography, the function of it goes to spread it across the photo being developed as the fixer restrains the image in place by deleting the hidden silver halides in the film. This method stops the film from further retaliating to light, thus excess chemicals cannot affect the photo anymore. While fixing is obsolete in the digital world today with cameras with digital sensors and photography applications, it is replaced with the rendering processes of the computer using the graphics processing unit (GPU) along with the main processes in the central processing unit (CPU).

While filming, developing, and fixing have become obsolete during this time. Photographic papers, on the other hand, didn't decline that far to be considered obsolete. While the functionality of the paper is in its property that, it is too light that it captures a latent image that is then enlarged to form a high-quality image based on gelatinous emulsions (Definitions.net, 2020), they can be also exposed to light using digital printers, hence it is still not that obsolete.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes that by analyzing the processes of developing a photograph on film and the digitization and the features of a popular image manipulation application, Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, there is a significant connection to the processing and developing techniques in modern graphic editing application softwares. It also shows the drastic improvements of the technologies used in taking up photos, as well as videos – a proof of scientific advancements that culminated into a methodology that is subject to change but for the sake of improving and making the nostalgia and documentation of memories better for the people that are living in the present time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher of this study would like to thank his laptop Rogue, for not failing to give up on this paper. Although this paper is totally constrained due to the lessened logistics and travels of the ongoing pandemic, the researcher had made this paper for the submission of the capstone earlier than much of the said deadline.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher would like to give recommendations on the analysis of the processes of developing photographs using conventional darkroom processes. The researcher found out that researching and retracking on old archives found on the internet have hindered the necessary information needed to assess the paper. Although there are accounts on many sites on the Internet regarding the following information, there is still a lack of resources that are collected for the references that are needed to do this study. It is hunched by the researcher that there is still an old archive of papers dating from the 1950's on the development of photographs under the company Kodak.

Also, the researcher hopes that whoever picks up upon this paper would want to have another improvement on the methodology by actually developing photographs using darkroom practices, as this would be a better paper overall if the pandemic didn't halt the plans of the researcher while doing this project. This may be the overall flaw of this paper, as it didn't focus entirely on the old methodology and rather looked upon the other development process on applications such as Adobe Photoshop Lightroom.

In this paper, the researcher would also want to detail more about the features of Adobe Photoshop Lightroom, but due to the time constrictions positioned upon the deadline of this paper, it is rather unfortunate to say that this paper still lacks more of the features in the software featured. This can be unfortunately documented on the Lightroom Presets, where the expenses necessary to get a preset during the time of the write-up seems to be impossible.

Finally, the researcher would want to test this out on the area of film and motion pictures to modern cinematic light processes and techniques of the modern day. This would include look-up tables (LUT's) that are varied and is used in every movie that is made for the big screen, to be able to apply it with studying it with color grading principles as seen in the paper of Cinco in 2019. Furthermore, the researcher stresses out that this would be better by also looking at the available codes for video processing applications, as this would give out a better perspective.

PHOTO CREDITS

The pictures and screenshots that are present in this paper are of Marc Andrie Bermundo. Other pictures that are shown have been tagged in with a source enclosed under a pair of parentheses. The chemical illustrations that are shown are drawn using Adobe Illustrator CC 2020.

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APPENDICES

Developed Photos

The following are the pictures that are developed for this research. There are many other pictures, but the researcher just intends to put it onto his personal profiles on his Behance account. Clearer versions of the pictures that are present here can be found at this link: [Marc Andrie Bermundo on Behance](#).

